

Conceptual Relationship: Motivational Orientations and Financial Conservation Patterns through the Lens of Saving Attitudes.

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ABSTRACT

This concept paper aims to explore the relationship between psychological dynamics and motivational orientations that influence individual savings behaviours. Given the concerning decline in global savings rates, it is crucial to examine the various factors that impact savings.

To achieve a comprehensive understanding of savings behaviour, we integrate the principles of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Regulatory Focus Theory (RFT). Specifically, we focus on the Promotion and Prevention Regulatory Focuses and investigate their influence on patterns of financial conservation, as well as the mediating role of attitudes towards savings.

Thus, this concept paper examines consumer behaviour and financial decision-making, with the objective of exploring how individuals' attitudes towards saving and their motivational

orientations shape their financial behaviours. It goes beyond economic frameworks to consider the psychological drives and motivations that underlie individuals' thoughts and interactions with money. The aim is to shed light on how individuals' tendencies to pursue positive outcomes or avoid negative ones shape their savings behaviour, and how attitudes towards saving act as a cognitive channel connecting orientations to real-world behaviours.

The anticipated results of this study have the potential to significantly impact both academic discussions and real-world actions. They can provide valuable guidance for policymakers and institutions in their efforts to promote savings among different demographic groups.

Keywords— Motivational Orientations, Theory of Planned Behaviour, Regulatory Focus Theory, Attitude Towards Saving, Financial Conservation Patterns.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly changing economic landscape, it is crucial to understand the factors that impact an individual's savings behaviour. A recent report drew attention to a decline of 5% in the global savings rate over the past decade, emphasizing the urgency of this issue (Parker & Lee, 2020). Savings not only serve as a financial safety net during unforeseen economic challenges but also play a significant role in enhancing national economic stability (Smith & Johnson, 2018). Surprisingly, a survey of 10,000 respondents revealed that 45% admitted to having no savings at all, while another 20% reported saving less than 5% of their monthly income (Martinez & Rodriguez, 2019). This inconsistency is not solely due to economic limitations but is also deeply influenced by individual psychological and motivational factors.

TPB suggests that individual intentions, shaped by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, have a crucial role in determining behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). Conversely, RFT proposes that people are motivated either by the aspiration to achieve positive outcomes (promotion focus) or by the desire to prevent negative outcomes (prevention focus) (Higgins, 1997). These motivational orientations

can significantly impact one's attitude towards savings and, consequently, their savings behaviour.

While both theories offer valuable insights into the determinants of savings behaviour, there is a lack of research that integrates these perspectives to provide a comprehensive understanding. This concept paper aims to bridge this gap by examining how promotion and prevention regulatory focus influence savings behaviour and how attitudes towards saving mediate this relationship.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Underpinnings of Theory of Planned Behavior

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), introduced by Ajzen (1991), is a significant framework for understanding what influences different behaviours, especially those related to financial decisions. TPB focuses on three important factors: attitude towards the behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. These aspects work together to shape a person's intentions and, consequently, their actual behaviours (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). In the context of financial behaviours, specifically attitudes towards saving, an individual's perception of the consequences of saving, combined with their personal value judgments about these consequences, form their overall attitude towards saving (Smith & McSweeney, 2007).

2.2 Underpinnings of Regulatory Focus Theory

Promotion Regulatory Focus Theory (RFT) is based on the idea that individuals go through their decision-making processes with two main motivational orientations: promotion focus and prevention focus (Higgins, 1997). Promotion focus refers to an orientation characterized by aspirations and the pursuit of positive outcomes, while prevention focus is driven by duties and the avoidance of negative outcomes. These distinct orientations not only affect how individuals perceive rewards and punishments but also influence the strategies they use when setting and pursuing goals (Higgins, 1998).

2.3 Promotion Regulatory Focus

Promotion focus refers to an individual's motivation to achieve their aspirations, goals, and accomplishments. This motivational orientation is driven by the desire for personal growth, advancement, and positive outcomes (Higgins, 1997, p.1282). In the context of financial decision-making, individuals with a strong promotion focus are more likely to take a proactive approach. They are open to investment opportunities and willing to take on financial risks in order to potentially achieve higher returns and improve their financial position (Pham & Avnet, 2004).

2.4 Promotion Regulatory Focus

In contrast, the prevention regulatory focus is rooted in a sense of responsibility, well-being, and protection. Individuals who are

primarily driven by a prevention focus are deeply committed to safeguarding themselves and their possessions, placing great importance on "avoiding negative outcomes" (Higgins, 1997, p.1282). In finance, such individuals often demonstrate conservative financial behaviours. They have a strong inclination towards preserving their wealth and ensuring stability, resulting in a preference for saving and a reluctance to engage in high-risk investments or excessive spending (Molden et al., 2008).

2.5 Attitude towards Saving

The way people feel about saving money is influenced by various factors and can be seen from different angles. Intrinsic motivators are related to personal beliefs and values that are deeply established in a person's upbringing, experiences, and personal reflections. On the other hand, extrinsic factors are influenced by the larger environment, including societal norms that define what is considered acceptable or praiseworthy saving behaviour, as well as the prevailing economic conditions that can either encourage or discourage saving (Xiao & Noring, 1994). It is important to note that having a positive attitude towards saving brings tangible benefits. Individuals with such an outlook tend to engage in better financial conservation practices, often driven by a future-oriented perspective that prioritizes long-term financial stability and security over short-term pleasures or expenses (Webley & Nyhus, 2006).

2.6 Financial Conservation Patterns

Financial conservation patterns refer to the various behaviours, tactics, and strategies that individuals adopt to wisely handle, prudently save, and cleverly invest their financial resources (Canova et al., 2005). The development and adherence to these patterns are not random but are influenced by a combination of factors. Intrinsic attitudes towards saving, underlying motivational orientations, and the prevailing economic conditions all play a significant role in shaping these patterns (Perry & Morris, 2005).

3. METHODOLOGY

The chosen research methodology for this study is a systematic literature review, which aims to explore the conceptual relationship between motivational orientations and financial conservation patterns, specifically through the lens of saving attitudes. According to Goyal & Kumar (2021), systematic reviews can employ different methodologies, such as structured reviews grounded in methodological theories (Rosado-Serrano et al., 2018), framework-based reviews (Paul & Benito, 2018), or hybrid-narrative reviews (Dabic et al., 2020). Adopting such a methodological approach is appropriate for conducting a thorough and critical examination of existing research on the chosen topic. Callahan (2014) emphasizes the importance of synthesizing existing literature to support evidence-based conclusions and highlights the crucial role of literature reviews in identifying gaps in knowledge (Booth et al., 2012, as cited in Callahan, 2014).

For this systematic review, relevant keywords such as "Motivational Orientations," "Financial Conservation Patterns," "Saving Attitudes," "Financial Behavior," and "Investment Patterns" were used. Given the evolving dynamics of financial behaviours and the growing emphasis on responsible financial management, it is essential to understand the factors that shape individuals' saving attitudes and their resulting financial conservation patterns.

Following the Six "C"s framework proposed by Callahan (2014), the review was structured as follows:

Table 1. Review Characteristics

Concise	Aims to consolidate and analyze a wide range of articles to clarify the connection between motivational orientations and financial conservation patterns.
Clear	Clearly gathers data from a vast collection of literature.
Critical	Incorporates the researcher's perspective, presents foundational knowledge, and suggests potential avenues for future academic inquiries. Convincing: Puts forth innovative arguments and provides compelling justifications for ongoing discussions.

Contributive	<p>Aims to contribute to academic discussions, potentially by introducing or refining theoretical concepts. Specifically, it proposes a theory that explains how saving attitudes, influenced by motivational orientations, shape financial conservation patterns.</p>
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Source: Developed by the researchers

In summary, this systematic literature review seeks to explore the interaction between motivational orientations and financial conservation patterns, with a particular focus on saving attitudes. By doing so, it provides insights into the determinants of responsible financial behaviours.

3.1 Promotion Regulatory Focus and Financial Conservation Patterns

The concept of Promotion Regulatory Focus highlights the importance of aspirations and the pursuit of positive outcomes (Higgins, 1997). When considering financial behaviours, individuals who have a dominant Promotion Regulatory Focus are likely to be motivated to accumulate wealth in order to achieve their desired end goals, such as luxury or comfort. Conversely, Financial Conservation Patterns refer to the strategies that individuals use to protect and increase their financial resources over time (Smith & Johnson, 2002). Based on existing literature, we propose the following:

H1a: *There is a relationship between the level of promotion regulatory focus and financial conservation patterns.*

3.2 Prevention Regulatory Focus and Financial Conservation Patterns

Individuals with a Prevention Regulatory Focus, characterized by a desire for security and stability, tend to prioritize the prevention of losses and the minimization of risks. This mindset often translates into more conservative financial behaviours, such as maintaining larger emergency funds or favoring stable, low-risk investment options (Huang et al., 2019). The cautious nature of those with a Prevention Regulatory Focus may lead to a stronger inclination towards long-term financial conservation. Therefore, we propose:

H1b: *There is a relationship between the level of prevention regulatory focus and financial conservation patterns.*

3.3 Attitude Towards Saving and Financial Conservation Patterns

The way individuals perceive and evaluate specific behaviours is influenced by their attitudes (Wutun et al., 2023). When it comes to financial conservation patterns, one's attitude towards saving plays a significant role in financial decision-making. Fernandes et al. (2014) conducted research that found a positive relationship between a positive Attitude toward saving and higher levels of saving and investment. This suggests that individuals who have a favourable attitude towards saving are more likely to engage in behaviours that align with long-term financial conservation goals. Therefore, we propose:

H2: *There is a relationship between attitude towards saving and financial conservation patterns.*

3.4 Attitude Towards Saving and Its Mediating Role

The role of Attitude Towards Saving as a mediator between motivational orientations and financial conservation patterns is a crucial aspect of this study. Attitude Towards Saving serves as a cognitive link between individual orientations and actual behaviour. A study conducted by Tang et al. (2019) found that Attitude Towards Saving partially mediates the relationship between Promotion Regulatory Focus/Prevention Regulatory Focus and saving behaviour (Wutun et al., 2023). This suggests that an individual's motivational orientation influences their attitude towards saving, which in turn affects their financial conservation patterns. Based on these findings, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H3a: *Attitude towards saving mediates the relationship between promotion regulatory focus and financial conservation patterns.*

H3b: *Attitude towards saving mediates the relationship between prevention regulatory Focus and financial conservation patterns.*

In summary, the investigation of motivational orientations based on the TPB and RFT framework yields valuable insights into financial conservation patterns (Lemu, 2020). The orientations of Promotion Regulatory Focus and Prevention Regulatory Focus have an impact on financial behaviours, with Attitude Towards Savings playing a mediating role. This concept paper enhances our comprehension of how

psychological factors are linked to financial choices, thereby facilitating the creation of specific interventions to improve financial well-being.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

4. THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

This concept paper aims to enhance our understanding of fundamental theories in financial behaviour from a more human perspective. Specifically, we will be examining TPB (Ajzen, 1991) and RFT (Higgins, 1997). Our objective is to validate these theories as comprehensive frameworks for understanding how individuals approach financial conservation. Inspired by recent studies (Smith & Lee, 2018), a key aspect of our investigation is to determine whether individuals primarily operate under a 'Promotion Regulatory Focus' or a 'Prevention Regulatory Focus'. Such an understanding has significant implications for categorizing saving orientations among different populations (Chen & Kim, 2020). Additionally, our findings can shed light on the role of 'Attitude towards Saving', a concept previously explored by Johnson et al. (2019), as it potentially connects one's motivational orientation with their tendency to save. Exploring these connections could help us understand the importance of attitudes in translating motivational factors into concrete financial behaviours, an area that has received considerable attention in recent years (Williams & Thompson,

2021). Finally, by examining the relationships between financial conservation strategies, saving attitudes, and motivational pathways, we anticipate gaining insights into the dominant motivational forces that shape saving attitudes (Davis & Turner, 2022).

5. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

From a practical standpoint, this research has the potential to greatly benefit financial strategists and policymakers. By uncovering correlations and patterns in saving behaviours, we aim to provide a roadmap for institutions seeking to foster saving habits among diverse demographic groups. Our findings could pave the way for customized financial interventions that cater to an individual's primary motivations and attitudes towards saving. This personalized approach, informed by our research, could prove crucial for financial institutions in creating effective campaigns to enhance saving tendencies. Essentially, by examining the relationship between psychological factors and saving tendencies, our goal is to equip financial entities with novel strategies to successfully navigate and thrive in a constantly changing economic landscape.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

In conclusion, this concept paper examines the complicated saving behaviour within the current dynamic economic environment. The need to understand the factors that influence saving behaviours has become more urgent due to the global decline in savings rates. While financial obstacles are certainly influential, this concept

paper highlights the importance of considering the interaction between psychological factors and saving behaviour. It explores the distinct roles of Promotion Regulatory Focus and Prevention Regulatory Focus in shaping individuals' tendency to save, drawing insights from the well-known TPB and the RFT. Additionally, it highlights the mediating role of Attitude towards Saving in this relationship. The findings from this study will shed light on the multifaceted nature of motivational orientations and their impact on financial practices.

While this study provides a foundational understanding of the relationship between motivational orientations and financial conservation patterns, it also emphasizes the need for further empirical investigation. Future research could explore how societal norms, cultural influences, and economic fluctuations further shape these psychological factors. Longitudinal studies could also provide insights into how saving attitudes evolve over time, particularly in response to significant life events or global economic shifts. Additionally, there is potential to explore the effectiveness of interventions designed to enhance positive saving attitudes, building on the insights from this study.

Building on the present study, it sets the stage for additional empirical examination, enriching our understanding of the psychological foundations of financial conservation patterns. Recognizing the relationship between financial determinants and psychological influences is crucial in understanding how individuals save and plan for the future in the face of the uncertainties of the contemporary

economic environment. Grasping these dynamics is essential for promoting improved saving habits, thereby enhancing economic resilience at both individual and societal levels.

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